

RESEARCH ARTICLE

SCIENTOMETRIC STUDY ON ARCHAEOLOGY, CULTURE, HERITAGE, TOURISM, PERCEIVED VALUE AND REVISIT INTENTION IN JORDAN

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ABSTRACT. *There have been numerous studies examining essential aspects of cultural and heritage tourism (CHT), but there is a lack of research that specifically focuses on the fundamental elements linked to the movement of structural knowledge in networks within the context of tourism performance. To fill this gap, this study comprehensively investigates the connections between cultural and heritage tourism, destination image, perceived value, and revisit intention. Tourism in Jordan is closely linked to archaeological sites, as monuments and historical sites are one of the main attractions for tourists. Jordan is characterized as a holy country, and its archaeological sites have great religious and historical significance, with many of these sites stemming from biblical accounts also known as biblical archaeology. The method of conducting a systematic literature review (SLR) was employed to choose and examine relevant research papers that were published in the last two decades. The findings indicate that cultural and heritage factors related to perceived value and revisit intention are not given much consideration by tourism researchers. The research findings also emphasize the significance of destination image, a crucial component for promoting CHT. The study also highlights the need for additional empirical research to clarify the role of CHT, destination image, and perceived value in predicting revisit intention, which is essential for the competitive and strategic management of tourism business organizations.*

KEYWORDS. *Scientometrics, scientometric, archaeology, Jordan, culture, heritage, tourism, destination image, perceived value, revisit intention, systematic.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Travel, tourism and archaeology, two of the largest economic sectors in the world, have long been used to boost national revenues (Turner 2017). Archaeological tourism in Jordan plays an important role in its growth, as it does in some countries around the world with archaeological tourism.

It not only boosts GDP, but also has a social impact, preserves identity and generates good income for the local community (Andereck *et al.* 2005). Examples of

these positive social outcomes include access to basic services and transport, as well as pride in local culture. Therefore, tourism is the lifeblood of countries with rich archaeological tourism resources.

CHT provides opportunities to visit or interact with places, artifacts, and activities that realistically represent the stories and people of the past and present (Hargrove 2002: 10). Many people seek out unique travel experiences that combine culture, education, entertainment and authenticity (Garrod & Fyall 2000, 2001; Hall & Zeppel 1990). Cultural and heritage tour-

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ism is an important global tourism market (Poria *et al.* 2003; Richards 2018).

However, attracting and retaining these cultural heritage tourists has become a fierce competition. Establishing a positive cultural tourism destination image and understanding the elements impacting it would be useful strategic choices for a destination to compete in foreign markets. In the tourist industry, revisit intention is considered a crucial element for the survival and growth of businesses (Ngoc & Trinh 2015). Tourists' intent to return is very important for businesses to expand and thrive (Ngoc & Trinh 2015).

The main factor is that frequent visits by visitors lower marketing and promotion costs (Loi *et al.* 2017; Kim *et al.* 2013). It also helps the tourism industry to be profitable and substantial (Alves *et al.* 2019; Stylos *et al.* 2017), and it is viewed to be essential for effective destination marketing (Beerli-Palacio & Martín-Santana 2018; Loi *et al.* 2017). Additionally, it is far less expensive to draw back regular customers than to draw in new ones (Chiu *et al.* 2012; Kim *et al.* 2013). Therefore, lowering marketing and promotion expenses by encouraging repeat customers and a positive visitor experience can result in achieving a competitive cost advantage, which may be the secret to a successful destination marketing strategy (Beerli-Palacio & Martín-Santana 2018). The quality of tourists' experiences and their evaluations of the services and facilities offered to them have a significant impact on the tourism industry because it is a service-oriented sector of the economy (Gani *et al.* 2019).

The tourism literature identifies the following factors as the key determinants of visitors returning to a place: destination image, service quality, satisfaction, and perceived value. These factors have a significant influence on visitors' behavior (Seetanah *et al.* 2020; Zhang *et al.* 2018; Chen & Tsai 2007; Allameh *et al.* 2015; Wang *et al.* 2017).

In more detail, research has tried to provide investigations of perceived value in the context of tourist destination experiences. Clear proof of a significant connection between perceived value and revisit intention to a destination has been shown by Domínguez-Quintero *et al.* (2019) and Lee *et al.* (2005). In their studies, they have also identified a distinction between the perceived value attributes for first-time and repeat tourists in tourism locations. Similarly, Prayogo *et al.* (2016) have shown empirically that perceived value mediates the perception of a destination image and revisit intention. In the context of tourism, particularly CHT, the more authen-

tic a destination, the higher its perceived value (Kolar & Zabkar 2010).

Perceived value is a crucial driver of consumption behavior, as it indicates customers' overall judgment of the utility of a product or service, which influences their decision-making along with their intention to repurchase and recommend (Lee *et al.* 2014). In the context of tourism, researchers have confirmed that more positive destination images are associated with higher perceived values (Cheng & Lu 2013). Similarly, it has been claimed that perceived value is a predictor of destination loyalty intention (Song *et al.* 2013). That is, when tourists receive good value for their money on a tour, they are more likely to promote it to others and return to the destination for future vacations. This study also assessed the variable of perceived value of archaeological tourism in Jordan.

Perceived value is a key driver of consumer behavior, reflecting the customer's overall assessment of the usefulness of a product or service. This evaluation significantly influences customers' decision-making process, including their intentions to repurchase or recommend archaeological tourism in Jordan.

Although previous studies have addressed the importance of these variables, there is a lack of research into the mediating role that the above-mentioned variables play. On the other hand, various scholars express their disappointment over the insufficient research conducted on cultural and heritage tourism, destination image, and revisit intention, despite the emergence and divergence of these theoretical connections in the tourism sector (Wu & Li 2017; Fang & Ariffin 2021; Zhang *et al.* 2020). The lack of literature in this area is significant because of how important the destination image and revisit intention are to the competitiveness, sustainability, and adaptability of tourism.

Therefore, this study aims to conduct a systematic literature review (SLR) to gather, analyze and summarize recent literature on the connections between cultural and heritage tourism, destination image, perceived value, and revisit intention, to create a summary of the theoretical links between these concepts. By conducting a systematic literature review, this study aims to uncover theoretical connections that have not received much attention within the scientific community. To achieve this goal, the paper presents a review of literature from different academic fields related to CHT, destination image, and revisit intention. Subsequently, the study endeavors to examine and organize the most pertinent research to identify gaps in knowledge by

carefully analyzing the relationships among CHT, destination image, perceived value, and revisit intention through thoughtful and insightful discussions. The results of this study address a gap in the tourism field by presenting theoretical evidence of prospective connections between the variables.

The article aimed to answer particular research questions about CHT. The authors carried out an extensive examination of relevant studies on the topic that were published in distinguished journals listed in the SSCI (Social Sciences Citation Index) and SCIE (Science Citation Index Expanded) between 2010 and 2022, using *Google Scholar* and *Scopus* for their search.

Question 1: What are the general characteristics of studies related to archaeological tourism?

Question 2: What are the structural features of research on archaeological tourism's intellectual dimension?

Question 3: What study areas are of interest to scholars in archaeological tourism? And exploring why tourists are drawn to archaeological sites?

And what are the understanding preferences for specific types of archaeological experiences, such as archaeological guided tours or independent exploration.

The rest of this article is organized in the following way: section 2 presents an overview of the literature review, section 3 outlines the methodology used in this study, section 4 reports the findings obtained from the research, and section 5 concludes the article by discussing the implications and conclusions of the study.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Cultural and Heritage Tourism (CHT)

Cultural and heritage tourism (CHT) is one of the most common types of tourism. CHT generally refers to visits to locations that reflect traditions and customs, art forms, events, and experiences that represent the nation and its people (Ariffin & Mansour 2018). Cultural heritage tourists visit to see sights such as historical buildings, old canals, battlegrounds, and old monuments, as well as artifacts and activities that accurately portray the stories and people of the past and present. Previous research has found that cultural tourism generates more income because cultural heritage tourists tend to stay longer and spend more money when compared to other types of tourists, because they are motivated to learn or experience the past or present beliefs,

practices, art, culture, or heritage that a group of identity people possesses (Mansour & Ariffin 2017).

According to Poria *et al.* (2003, 2004), one of the incentives for tourists to participate in heritage tourism is their desire to observe and learn about the physical characteristics of the site as well as its historical context. Cultural heritage tourists are people who go to cultural heritage sites as a hobby and have an interest in learning about other people's cultures. To accomplish their objective, tourists will travel more frequently, and farther, spending more money to obtain the knowledge that they seek (Partners for Livable Communities 2014). Cultural heritage tourism offers a variety of lessons and values that enrich current generations' identities based on historical events.

2.2 Destination Image

Destination image is described as an individual's feelings about a location (Hunt 1975), and it was initially recognized as an important aspect of the destination selection process in 1970 (Mayo 1975). Most researchers agreed that a location with a favorable and unique image has a greater possibility of being chosen as a tourist destination (Baloglu & Love 2005; Toral *et al.* 2018; Um & Crompton 1990). Crompton (1979) provided the most commonly referenced definition of destination image as "the sum of all beliefs, ideas, and impressions that people associate with a destination."

Baloglu and McCleary (1999) found later that a person's characteristics influenced the formation of a destination image. According to Al-Azri and Morrison (2006), the destination image is the perception that tourists have of a tourist destination based on a combination of their beliefs, feelings, impressions, ideas, and knowledge about a certain location. Perception of a destination can be formed from a variety of sources of information, including personal experience (Cavlak & Cop 2019). This perception can be formed before, during, and after visiting a location (Ioradanova & Styliadis 2019). Furthermore, the destination image is combining of both cognitive and affective images (Birdir *et al.* 2018; Lin *et al.* 2007). The cognitive image is concerned with knowledge about the destination, while the affective image is concerned with people's feelings and emotions about the destination. According to Qu *et al.* (2011), tourists select their destinations based on their distinctiveness. The focus for marketing the destination is on creating a distinct destination image. Unique and distinctive qualities have been used to differenti-

ate tourist destinations from similar destinations, to create a mental image of the place in the minds of target tourists, and to boost their attention to the destinations. According to the foregoing discussion, in this study, the term “destination image” refers to an interacting set of personal normative beliefs, perceptions, expectations, ideas, emotions, and feelings held by different individuals (including visitors and non-visitors) toward a certain place, which can change over time. According to a review of the literature on cultural heritage, a country’s image is made up of various characteristics. Tourism attractions, general infrastructures, archaeological monuments, social environment, transportation services, accommodation, supported services, food, personal safety, and communication are some of the common elements that constitute the image of a cultural heritage tourism destination (Kempiak *et al.* 2017; Wu & Li 2017; Poria *et al.* 2004).

According to Hankinson (2004) and Hwang and Lee (2019), the significance of destination image can be summed up as knowing how the destination affects tourist satisfaction and how to create a positive brand image to increase the destination’s attractiveness and consequently boost economic development there. As a result, destination image has been regarded as a foundation of tourism development for strategically accessing the destination image to potential tourists to promote a tourism location. However, achieving tourist happiness is difficult since destination image fluctuates with educational, emotional, and social experiences (Prayag *et al.* 2017). Furthermore, political conditions, destination surroundings, price, travel costs, festivals, history, accessibility, and hospitality are all factors used to assess a destination image (Girma & Singh 2019). Due to its profound influence on tourists’ subjective impression, ensuing behavior and destination choice, the power of a location’s image has received widespread recognition (Zhang *et al.* 2018). Therefore, empirical studies are needed to shed light on the impact of CHT on destination image and perceived value, which is critical for the competitiveness and long-term success of the tourism industry.

3. RESEARCH METHOD

3.1 Search and Information Sources

In this study, the researchers chose to use an interpretive approach for their systematic literature review

(SLR) rather than a more general summary approach. They followed the methodology proposed by Miles and Huberman (1994), which focused on reducing, displaying, and verifying data. During the data reduction phase, they identified categories such as “cultural heritage tourism,” “destination image,” “perceived value,” and “revisit intention,” and sorted research articles into those categories. This methodology is similar to content analysis, where categories are established first, and then studies are compared and tabulated into the relevant categories for the study (Azinuddin *et al.* 2022). This study gathered articles from *Google Scholar* and *Scopus* advanced search engines. *Google Scholar* and *Scopus* were used as database sources due to their extensive archive of research publications. To begin the search process, we created a search string that included terms such as “cultural heritage tourism,” “destination image,” “perceived value,” and “revisit intention” in the title, abstract, or keywords of the articles. We used various combinations of these terms to find relevant tourism research articles, which we then matched through subsequent searches: a) “tourism,” “cultural heritage,” “destination image;” b) “tourism,” “cultural heritage,” “perceived value;” c) “tourism,” “cultural heritage,” “revisit intention;” d) “tourism,” “cultural heritage,” “destination image,” “perceived value;” f) “tourism,” “cultural heritage,” “destination image,” “revisit intention.”

The research papers chosen for the SLR were then sourced from general management and tourist publications using a variety of significant databases, including Wiley, Taylor & Francis, Sage, Emerald, Elsevier, etc. The SLR only contains items that were released between 2010 and 2022.

3.2 Data Collection Process and Article Screening

In order to conduct the research, the authors chose to concentrate exclusively on peer-reviewed journal articles. They disregarded papers, books, and editorial materials as they deemed them to be of little significance in terms of knowledge development (Law *et al.* 2012). Furthermore, articles published in languages other than English were not included in the study.

The researchers created data extraction forms to locate the relevant articles and gain insight into the methods used in studies on cultural heritage tourism, destination image, perceived value, and revisit intention. To ensure accuracy, a structured data extraction format was used to evaluate each article based on its quality. The

Figure 1. Systematic review paper selection procedure.

extracted data included information such as the author, year, title, journal, abstract, keywords, research purpose, topics, detailed topics, research methods and data source.

To gain a comprehensive understanding of research on cultural heritage tourism, destination image, perceived value, and revisit intention, the researchers developed data extraction forms. Each article was evalu-

ated based on its quality using a structured data extraction format, which included information such as the author, year, title, journal, abstract, keywords, research purpose, topics, detailed topics, research methods and data source. The integration of both sources resulted in 322 downloads of unique content. Manual double-checking was then performed by speed-reading titles, abstracts, keywords, the first paragraph, and as much content as needed from relevant parts. Any journals that did not pertain to the focus of this study were eliminated by the authors. Furthermore, the inclusion requirements demanded that the papers be published in international peer-reviewed journals, excluding books, book chapters, and conference papers.

To screen for relevant articles, the researchers analyzed the context of the keywords and abstracts presented in each article. This process helped to distinguish articles that were directly related to CHT, destination image, perceived value, and revisit intention from those that were not. The study found that 145 articles were relevant to the topics of cultural heritage tourism, destination image, perceived value, and revisit intention. The researchers then analyzed the contents of these articles and categorized them into those where these topics were the primary focus and those where they were secondary.

Finally, 89 articles that addressed these topics as the main issues were selected for the systematic review (as shown in Figure 1). This screening process was conducted by the researchers independently, and any differences in data interpretation were resolved through discussions among the authors. These were then organized and tagged by the following classification categories: author(s), year of publication, journal, title, CHT, destination image, perceived value, and revisit intention (Table 1).

3.3 Data Analysis

This study categorized the chosen articles according to a number of criteria in order to respond to research question one (What are the general characteristics of studies related to archaeological tourism?). First, the volume of publications pertaining to linked studies per year and per region was examined. The publishing patterns of journals pertaining to CHT, destination image, perceived value, and revisit intention were then examined. Finally, the research methodologies and viewpoints that were used in the connected studies were examined.

To address the second research question (What are the structural features of research on archaeological tourism's intellectual dimension?), this study developed a bibliographic map that illustrates the co-occurrence of keywords that indicate the main scientific themes of each study. The study used the VOSviewer software in conjunction with the multidimensional scaling technique to generate a bibliographic map that reflects the interrelationships between research keywords (Van Eck & Waltman 2010). The software utilized mapping techniques to establish the location of keywords on the map and clustering techniques to construct clusters through the allocation of often co-occurring terms (Borg & Groenen 2005).

With regard to the third research question (What study areas are of interest to scholars in archaeological tourism?), an analysis was conducted on the research topics from the chosen articles that are relevant to this field. Initially, the research topics were grouped into categories to gain a general understanding of the research trends in CHT. Furthermore, the proportion of topics in each category was examined to determine which ones were more prominent in the research on this topic. Lastly, a detailed examination was made of the individual topics within each category to identify specific research trends in CHT.

4. STUDY FINDINGS

An analysis of the general characteristics of the selected studies was done to provide the first research question with an answer. Research on CHT increased gradually between 2010 and 2022. A total of 2–8 articles on CHT were published every year on average between 2010 and 2016 (ranging from 2 to 8). However, from 2017 to 2022, the number of papers published increased to 12–25 per year, demonstrating a noticeably rising interest in CHT. Figure 2 provides an example of this pattern.

Research on CHT, destination image, perceived value, and revisit intention has been conducted in various regions, as shown in Table 2. The majority of the research (77.5%) was carried out in Asia, with 69 papers. Europe was the second most researched region, with 11 papers. Among the Asian countries, China had the most publications (14 papers) on CHT, destination image, and revisit intention. In Europe, Spain led the research in this area with 4 papers. Africa, North America, and the Middle East had fewer publications, ranging from 1 to 6 in the last 12 years. This indicates

Table 1a. Summary of SLR findings: article information and research variables.

Article Information			Research Variables				
Author(s)	Article Title	Journal	Cultural and Heritage Tourism	Destination Image	Perceived Value	Revisit Intention	
1	Chen & Funk (2010)	Exploring destination image, experience and revisit intention: A comparison of sport and non-sport tourist perceptions	<i>Journal of Sport & Tourism</i>	X	✓	X	✓
2	Wang, Wu & Yuan (2010)	Exploring visitors' experiences and intention to revisit a heritage destination: The case for Lukang, Taiwan	<i>Journal of Quality Assurance in Hospitality & Tourism</i>	✓	✓	X	✓
3	Park & Njite (2010)	Relationship between destination image and tourists' future behavior: Observations from Jeju Island, Korea	<i>Asia Pacific Journal of Tourism Research</i>	X	✓	X	✓
4	Ramkissoon & Uysal (2011)	The effects of perceived authenticity, information search behaviour, motivation and destination imagery on cultural behavioural intentions of tourists	<i>Current Issues in Tourism</i>	✓	✓	X	✓
5	Ramkissoon, Uysal & Brown (2011)	Relationship between destination image and behavioral intentions of tourists to consume cultural attractions	<i>Journal of Hospitality Marketing & Management</i>	✓	✓	X	X
6	Canny & Hidayat (2012)	The influence of service quality and tourist satisfaction on future behavioral intentions: The case study of Borobudur Temple as a UNESCO world culture heritage destination	<i>International Proceedings of Economics Development & Research</i>	✓	X	X	✓
7	Mohamad, Abdullah & Mokhlis (2012)	Tourists' evaluations of destination image and future behavioral intention: the case of Malaysia	<i>Journal of Management and Sustainability</i>	✓	✓	X	✓
8	Moon, Ko, Connaughton, & Lee (2013)	A mediating role of destination image in the relationship between event quality, perceived value, and behavioral intention	<i>Journal of Sport & Tourism</i>	X	✓	✓	X
9	Cheng & Lu (2013)	Destination Image, Novelty, Hedonics, Perceived Value, and Revisiting Behavioral Intention for Island Tourism	<i>Asia Pacific Journal of Tourism Research</i>	X	✓	✓	✓
10	Calver & Page (2013)	Enlightened hedonism: Exploring the relationship of service value, visitor knowledge and interest, to visitor enjoyment at heritage attractions	<i>Tourism Management</i>	✓	X	✓	✓
11	Su & Hsu (2013)	Service fairness, consumption emotions, satisfaction, and behavioral intentions: The experience of Chinese heritage tourists	<i>Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing</i>	✓	X	X	✓
12	Song, Su & Li (2013)	The indirect effects of destination image on destination loyalty intention through tourist satisfaction and perceived value: The bootstrap approach	<i>Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing</i>	X	✓	✓	X
13	Herstani, Suhud, & Wibowo (2014)	Three Modified Models to Predict Intention of Indonesian Tourists to Revisit Sydney	<i>European Journal of Business and Management</i>	X	✓	✓	✓
14	Chew & Jahari (2014)	Destination image as a mediator between perceived risks and	<i>Tourism management</i>	X	✓	X	✓
15	Chang, Backman & Chih Huang (2014)	revisit intention: A case of post-disaster Japan Creative tourism: a preliminary examination of creative tourists' motivation, experience, perceived value and revisit intention	<i>International Journal of Culture, Tourism, and Hospitality Research</i>	X	X	✓	✓
16	Wong & Cheng (2014)	Exploring the effects of heritage site image on souvenir shopping attitudes: The moderating role of perceived cultural difference	<i>Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing</i>	✓	✓	X	X
17	Pratminingsih, Rudatin & Rimenta (2014)	Roles of motivation and destination image in predicting tourist revisit intention: A case of Bandung-Indonesia	<i>International Journal of Innovation, Management and Technology</i>	X	✓	X	✓
18	Nguyen & Cheung (2014)	The classification of heritage tourists: A case of Hue city, Vietnam	<i>International Business Research</i>	✓	✓	X	X
19	Aliman, Hashim, Wahid & Harudin (2014)	Tourist expectation, perceived quality and destination image: Effects on perceived value and satisfaction of tourists visiting langkawi Island, Malaysia	<i>Asian Journal of Business and Management</i>	X	✓	✓	X
20	Teo, Khan & Abd Rahim (2014)	Understanding cultural heritage visitor behavior: the case of Melaka as world heritage city	<i>Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences</i>	✓	✓	✓	X
21	Lban, Kasli & Bezirgan (2015)	Effects of destination image and total perceived value on tourists' behavioral intentions: an investigation of domestic festival tourists	<i>Tourism Analysis</i>	X	✓	✓	✓
22	Ramseook-Munhurrun, Seebaluck & Naidoo (2015)	Examining the structural relationships of destination image, perceived value, tourist satisfaction and loyalty: case of Mauritius.	<i>Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences</i>	X	✓	✓	X
23	Allameh, Pool, Jaber, Salehzadeh & Asadi (2015)	Factors influencing sport tourists' revisit intentions: The role and effect of destination image, perceived quality, perceived value and satisfaction.	<i>Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics</i>	X	✓	✓	✓

Article Information			Research Variables				
Author(s)	Article Title	Journal	Cultural and Heritage Tourism	Destination Image	Perceived Value	Revisit Intention	
24	Wang & Leou (2015)	A study of tourism motivation, perceived value and destination loyalty for Macao cultural and heritage tourists	<i>International Journal of marketing studies</i>	✓	X	✓	X
25	Lu, Chi & Liu (2015)	Authenticity, involvement, and image: Evaluating tourist experiences at historic districts	<i>Tourism management</i>	✓	✓	X	X
26	Goh (2015)	Investigating revisit intentions for the boutique hotels of Penang-A UNESCO world heritage site	<i>Asian Social Science</i>	✓	X	X	✓
27	Ranjbarian & Pool (2015)	The impact of perceived quality and value on tourists' satisfaction and intention to revisit Nowshahr city of Iran	<i>Journal of Quality Assurance in Hospitality & Tourism</i>	X	✓	✓	✓
28	Wang, Yang, Han & Shi (2016)	Car Tourism in Xinjiang: The Mediation Effect of Perceived Value and	<i>Sustainability</i>	X	✓	✓	X

that research on CHT, destination image, and revisit intention is mainly focused on Asia and Europe. Archaeology, as a foundation, interlinks and overlaps with

heritage: it provides the physical evidence (artifacts and monuments) that supports cultural narratives and heritage conservation. Heritage ensures that archaeologi-

Table 1b. Summary of SLR findings: article information and research variables.

29	Stylos, Vassiliadis, Bellou & Andronikidis (2016)	Destination images, holistic images and personal normative beliefs: Predictors of intention to revisit a destination	<i>Tourism management</i>	X	✓	X	✓
30	Julaimi, Abdul Talib & Suhaimi (2016)	International tourists revisit intention: A case of the United Arab Emirates	<i>Journal of Tourism, Hospitality & Culinary Arts</i>	X	✓	X	✓
31	Basaran (2016)	Examining the relationships of cognitive, affective, and conative destination image: A research on Safranbolu, Turkey	<i>International Business Research</i>	✓	✓	X	X
32	Lee, Phau, Hughes, Li & Quintal (2016)	Heritage tourism in Singapore Chinatown: A perceived value approach to authenticity and satisfaction	<i>Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing</i>	✓	X	✓	X
33	Chen, Leask & Phou (2016)	Symbolic, experiential and functional consumptions of heritage tourism destinations: The case of Angkor world heritage site, Cambodia	<i>International Journal of Tourism Research</i>	✓	X	X	✓
34	Wu & Li (2017)	A study of experiential quality, perceived value, heritage image, experiential satisfaction, and behavioral intentions for heritage tourists	<i>Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Research</i>	✓	X	✓	X
35	Stylydis, Belhassen & Shani (2017)	Destination image, on-site experience and behavioural intentions: path analytic validation of a marketing model on domestic tourists	<i>Current Issues in Tourism</i>	X	✓	X	✓
36	Prayogo & Kusumawardhana (2017)	Examining relationships of destination image, service quality, e-WOM, and revisit intention to Sabang Island, Indonesia	<i>Asia Pacific Management and Business Application</i>	X	✓	X	✓
37	Stylos, Bellou, Andronikidis & Vassiliadis (2017)	Linking the dots among destination images, place attachment, and revisit intentions: A study among British and Russian tourists	<i>Tourism management</i>	X	✓	X	✓
38	Kempiak, Hollywood, Bolan & McMahon-Beattie (2017)	The heritage tourist: An understanding of the visitor experience at heritage attractions	<i>International Journal of Heritage Studies</i>	✓	X	X	✓
39	Khuong & Phuong (2017)	The effects of destination image, perceived value, and service quality on tourist satisfaction and word-of-mouth—A study in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam	<i>International Journal of Trade, Economics and Finance</i>	X	✓	✓	X
40	Artuger & Cetinsoz (2017)	The impact of destination image and the intention to Revisit: A study Regarding Arab Tourists	<i>European Scientific Journal</i>	X	✓	X	✓
41	Bintarti & Kurniawan (2017)	A study of revisit intention: Experiential quality and image of Muara Beting tourism site in Bekasi District	<i>European Research Studies Journal</i>	X	✓	X	✓
42	Kani, Aziz, Sambasivan & Bojei (2017)	Antecedents and outcomes of destination image of Malaysia	<i>Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management</i>	X	✓	X	✓
43	Loi, So, Lo & Fong (2017)	Does the quality of tourist shuttles influence revisit intention through destination image and satisfaction? The case of Macao	<i>Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management</i>	X	✓	X	✓
44	Su, Hsu & Swanson (2017)	The effect of tourist relationship perception on destination loyalty at a world heritage site in China: The mediating role of overall destination satisfaction and trust	<i>Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Research</i>	✓	✓	X	✓
45	Mansour & Ariffin (2017)	The effects of local hospitality, commercial hospitality and experience quality on behavioral intention in cultural heritage tourism	<i>Journal of Quality Assurance in Hospitality & Tourism</i>	✓	X	X	✓
46	Abdullah & Lui (2018)	Satisfaction Drivers and revisit intention of International Tourists in Malaysia	<i>Journal of Tourism, Hospitality and Environment Management</i>	X	✓	X	✓
47	Kim (2018)	The impact of memorable tourism experiences on loyalty behaviors: The mediating effects of destination image and satisfaction	<i>Journal of Travel Research</i>	X	✓	X	✓
48	Zhang, Wu & Buhalis (2018)	A model of perceived image, memorable tourism experiences and revisit intention	<i>Journal of destination marketing & management</i>	X	✓	X	✓

Table 1 (con't)						
Author(s)	Article Title	Journal	Research Variables			
			Cultural and Heritage Tourism	Destination Image	Perceived Value	Revisit Intention
49	Chen & Rahman (2018)	<i>Tourism management perspectives</i>	✓	X	X	✓
50	Su & Huang (2018)	<i>Sustainability</i>	X	✓	X	✓
51	Suhartanto, Clemes & Wibisono (2018)	<i>Tourism Culture & Communication</i>	✓	✓	X	X
52	Hernández - Mogollón, Duarte & Folgado-Fernández (2018)	<i>Journal of Destination Marketing & Management</i>	✓	✓	X	X
53	Cheng, Kuo, Chang & Chen (2019)	<i>Journal of China Tourism Research</i>	X	✓	✓	✓
54	Mai, Nguyen & Nguyen (2019)	<i>Sustainability</i>	X	✓	✓	X
55	Moon & Han (2019)	<i>Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing</i>	X	✓	✓	X
56	Deveci & Dedeoğlu (2019)	<i>Tourism Management Perspectives</i>	X	✓	✓	✓

cal finds and cultural traditions are protected and shared with future generations. Culture gives meaning to archaeological finds and shapes how heritage is evaluated and interpreted.

Table 3 shows that the 89 articles chosen for examination were published across various academic journals. Among them, *Sustainability*, *Journal of Quality Assurance in Hospitality & Tourism*, *Journal of Travel & Tour-*

Table 1c. Summary of SLR findings: article information and research variables.

57	Sharma & Nayak (2019)	Understanding memorable tourism experiences as the determinants of tourists' behaviour	<i>International Journal of Tourism Research</i>	X	✓	X	✓
58	Jeong & Kim (2020)	A study of event quality, destination image, perceived value, tourist satisfaction, and destination loyalty among sport tourists	<i>Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics</i>	X	✓	✓	X
59	Hasan, Abdullah, Islam & Neela (2020)	An integrated model for examining tourists' revisit intention to beach tourism destinations.	<i>Journal of Quality Assurance in Hospitality & Tourism</i>	X	X	✓	✓

Table 1 (con't)

Article Information			Research Variables				
Author(s)	Article Title	Journal	Cultural and Heritage Tourism	Destination Image	Perceived Value	Revisit Intention	
60	Ha Nam Khanh (2020)	How Destination Image Factors Affect Domestic Tourists Revisit Intention to Ba Ria-Vung Tau Province, Vietnam	<i>Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business</i>	X	✓	X	✓
61	Jin, Choi, Lee & Ahmad (2020)	Effects of place attachment and image on revisit intention in an ecotourism destination: Using an extended model of goal-directed behavior	<i>Sustainability</i>	X	✓	X	✓
62	Huete Alcocer, & López Ruiz, (2020)	The role of destination image in tourist satisfaction: the case of a heritage site	<i>Economic research-Ekonomska istraživanja</i>	✓	✓	X	X
63	Hasan, Abdullah, Islam & Neela (2020)	An integrated model for examining tourists' revisit intention to beach tourism destinations	<i>Journal of Quality Assurance in Hospitality & Tourism</i>	X	X	✓	✓
64	Nguyen Viet, Dang & Nguyen (2020)	Revisit intention and satisfaction: The role of destination image, perceived risk, and cultural contact	<i>Cogent Business & Management</i>	X	✓	X	✓
65	Jimber del Río, Hernández-Rojas, Vergara-Romero & Dancausa Millán(2020)	Loyalty in heritage tourism: The case of Córdoba and its four world heritage sites	<i>International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health</i>	✓	X	✓	X
66	Su, Nguyen, Nguyen & Tran (2020)	The link between travel motivation and satisfaction towards a heritage destination: The role of visitor engagement, visitor experience and heritage destination image	<i>Tourism Management Perspectives</i>	✓	✓	X	X
67	Realino, Múgiono & Moko (2021)	The Effect of Customer Experiential Quality on Revisit Intention with Positive Emotion and Perceived Value as Mediation Variables	<i>The International Journal of Social Sciences World</i>	✓	X	✓	✓
68	Fang & Ariffin (2021)	Cultural heritage tourism: Determinants of behavioral intention to visit a historical city from experiential perspectives.	<i>Journal of Tourism, Hospitality and Environment Management</i>	✓	X	X	✓
69	Prayogo (2021)	Exploring of E-Wom, Destination Image and Perceived Value Toward Return to Visit.	<i>International Journal of Applied Sciences in Tourism and Events</i>	X	✓	✓	X
70	Soliman (2021)	Extending the theory of planned behavior to predict tourism destination revisit intention	<i>International Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Administration</i>	X	✓	X	✓

71	Cham, Lim, Sia, Cheah & Ting (2021)	Medical tourism destination image and its relationship with the intention to revisit: A study of Chinese medical tourists in Malaysia	<i>Journal of China tourism research</i>	X	✓	✓	✓
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Table 1 (con't)

Article Information			Research Variables				
Author(s)	Article Title	Journal	Cultural and Heritage Tourism	Destination Image	Perceived Value	Revisit Intention	
72	Kamel (2021)	Role of tour guides in tourism promotion and impact on destination image and tourist revisit intention in Egypt: a PLS-SEM model	<i>Journal of Association of Arab Universities for Tourism and Hospitality</i>	X	✓	X	✓
73	Čulić, Vujičić, Kalimić, Dunjić, Stankov, Kovačić... & Anđelković, (2021)	Rookie Tourism Destinations—The Effects of Attractiveness Factors on Destination Image and Revisit Intention with the Satisfaction Mediation Effect	<i>Sustainability</i>	X	✓	X	✓
74	Hernandez-Rojas, del Río, Fernández & Vergara-Romero (2021)	The cultural and heritage tourist, SEM analysis: the case of The Citadel of the Catholic King	<i>Heritage science</i>	✓	X	✓	X
75	Realino & Moko (2021)	The Effect of customer experiential quality on revisit intention with positive emotion and perceived value as mediation variables	<i>The International Journal of Social Sciences World</i>	X	X	✓	✓
76	Hamid, Mohamad & Suki (2021)	Tourists' revisit intention to UNESCO world heritage sites in a developing nation: Investigating the mediating role of place dependence	<i>Journal of Vacation Marketing</i>	✓	X	X	✓
77	Rasoolimane sh, Seyfi, Hall & Hatamifar (2021)	Understanding memorable tourism experiences and behavioural intentions of heritage tourists	<i>Journal of Destination Marketing & Management</i>	✓	✓	X	✓
78	Xu, Cheung, Lovett, Duan, Pei & Liang (2021)	Understanding the influence of user-generated content on tourist loyalty behavior in a cultural World Heritage Site	<i>Tourism Recreation Research</i>	X	✓	X	✓
79	Abbasi, Kumaravelu, Goh & Singh (2021)	Understanding the intention to revisit a destination by expanding the theory of planned behaviour (TPB)	<i>Spanish Journal of Marketing-ESIC</i>	X	✓	✓	✓
80	Ernawadi & Putra (2021)	Authenticity and Walkability of Iconic Heritage Destination in Bandung Indonesia	<i>International Journal of Science, Technology & Management</i>	✓	X	X	✓
81	Mandić & Kennell (2021)	Smart governance for heritage tourism destinations: Contextual factors and destination management organization perspectives	<i>Tourism Management Perspectives</i>	✓	✓	X	X
82	Damanik & Yusuf (2022)	Effects of perceived value, expectation, visitor management, and visitor satisfaction on revisit intention to Borobudur Temple, Indonesia	<i>Journal of Heritage Tourism</i>	X	X	✓	✓
83	Libre, Manalo & Lakisto (2022)	Factors influencing Philippines tourist revisit intention: The role and effect of destination image, tourist experience,	<i>International Journal of Quantitative Research and Modeling</i>	X	✓	✓	✓

ism Marketing, Tourism Management, and Tourism Management Perspectives had the highest number of publications related to topics such as CHT tourism, desti-

nation image, and revisit intention. Following closely behind were the *Journal of Destination Marketing & Management*, *Journal of China Tourism Research*, *Jour-*

Table 1d. Summary of SLR findings: article information and research variables.

	perceived value, and tourist satisfaction						
84	Investigating the mediating role of visitor satisfaction in the relationship between memorable tourism experiences and behavioral intentions in heritage tourism context	Rasoolimaneh, Seyfi, Rather & Hall (2022)	Tourism Review	✓	✗	✗	✓
85	Measuring Revisit Intentions of Green Resorts In Malaysia: The Role of Perceived Value And Environmental Concern	NRA, Patwary & Rashid (2022)	GeoJournal of Tourism and Geosites	✗	✗	✓	✓
86	Perceived value of, and experience with, a World Heritage Site in China—the case of Kaiping Diaolou and villages in China	Zhang, Yang, Wang & Ma (2022)	Journal of Heritage Tourism	✓	✗	✓	✗
87	The Effect of Event Image on Revisit Intention with Perceived Value as a Mediating Variable	Yosa, Suroso & Setyanto (2022)	International Journal of Sustainable Competitiveness Advantage	✗	✗	✓	✓
88	The influence of international tourists' destination image of Pakistan on behavioral intention: The roles of travel experience and media exposure	Nazir, Yasin, Tat, Khaliq & Mehmood (2022)	International Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Administration	✗	✓	✗	✓
89	The effect of brand heritage in tourists' intention to revisit	Mohammed, Mahmoud & Hinson (2022)	Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Insights	✓	✗	✗	✓
Number of Papers Reviewed				36	62	36	62

nal of Hospitality and Tourism Management, and Asia Pacific Journal of Tourism Research, each with two or three publications.

Table 2. Articles per region.

Regions	No.	%	Countries
Asia	69	77.4	China (14) Malaysia (12) Indonesia (12) Taiwan (4) Korea (4) Vietnam (7) Turkey (4) Iran (4) India (1) Singapore (1) Cambodia (1) Philippines (1) Bangladesh (2) Pakistan (1) Japan (1)
Europe	11	12.4	Spain (4) Sweden (1) UK (2) Greece (2) Ireland (1) Serbia (1)
North America	1	1.1	USA (1)
Middle East	2	2.2	United Arab Emirates (1) Israel (1)
Africa	6	6.8	Mauritius (3) Egypt (2) Ghana (1)
Total	89	100.0	

Out of the 89 chosen articles, research was conducted using two different methods. The selected papers were analyzed using either quantitative analysis or a combination of quantitative and qualitative analysis. The majority of the papers, 85 in total, utilized quantitative analysis with questionnaire surveys being the primary research method. Only four of the papers used a mixed analysis approach.

Figure 2. Article distribution from 2010 to 2022.

Table 3a. Publications per journal.

Journal	No.	%
Journal of Quality Assurance in Hospitality & Tourism	5	5.6
Tourism Management	5	5.6
Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing	5	5.6
Sustainability	5	5.6
Tourism management perspectives	4	4.5
Journal of destination marketing & Management	3	3.5
Asia Pacific Journal of Tourism Research	2	2.3
Journal of Sport & Tourism	2	2.3
Current Issues in Tourism	2	2.3
International Business Research	2	2.3
Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences	2	2.3
Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics	2	2.3
International Journal of Tourism Research	2	2.3
Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Research	2	2.3
Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management	2	2.3
Journal of Tourism, Hospitality and Environment Management	2	2.3
The International Journal of Social Sciences World	2	2.3
International Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Administration	2	2.3
Journal of Heritage Tourism	2	2.3
Journal of China Tourism Research	2	2.3
Journal of Hospitality Marketing & Management	1	1.1
International Proceedings of Economics Development & Research	1	1.1

4.1 Intellectual Structure Based on Keywords

This study explored keywords linked to cultural heritage tourism studies, destination image, and revisit intention to address research question 2. The VOSviewer software (Van Eck & Waltman 2010) was used to examine keyword co-occurrence (Figure 3).

Tourism centered on “cultural heritage” was the first important keyword. Increasing the sustainability of cultural heritage tourism can be accomplished in part by pursuing win-win relationships (Teo *et al.* 2014). Teo, Khan and Abd Rahim (2014) found that providing cultural heritage tourism products and enhancing the relationship between cultural heritage tourism and destination image can significantly improve the economic and ecological sustainability of heritage sites. According to Mansour and Ariffin (2017), heritage tourism refers to an economic activity that utilizes inherited and sociocultural assets to draw in tourists. The study found

Table 3b. Publications per journal.

Journal of Management and Sustainability	1	1.1
European Journal of Business and Management	1	1.1
International Journal of Culture, Tourism, and Hospitality Research	1	1.1
International Journal of Innovation, Management and Technology	1	1.1
Asian Journal of Business and Management	1	1.1
Tourism Analysis	1	1.1
International Journal of marketing studies	1	1.1
Asian Social Science	1	1.1
Journal of Tourism, Hospitality & Culinary Arts	1	1.1
Asia Pacific Management and Business Application	1	1.1
International Journal of Heritage Studies	1	1.1
International Journal of Trade, Economics and Finance	1	1.1
European Scientific Journal	1	1.1
European Research Studies Journal	1	1.1
Journal of Travel Research	1	1.1
Tourism Culture & Communication	1	1.1
Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business	1	1.1
Economic research-Ekonomska istraživanja	1	1.1
Cogent Business & Management	1	1.1
International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health	1	1.1
International Journal of Applied Sciences in Tourism and Events	1	1.1
Journal of Association of Arab Universities for Tourism and Hospitality	1	1.1
Heritage science	1	1.1
Journal of Vacation Marketing	1	1.1
Tourism Recreation Research	1	1.1
Spanish Journal of Marketing-ESIC	1	1.1
International Journal of Science, Technology & Management	1	1.1
International Journal of Quantitative Research and Modeling	1	1.1
Tourism Review	1	1.1
GeoJournal of Tourism and Geosites	1	1.1
International Sustainable Competitiveness Advantage	1	1.1
Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Insights	1	1.1
Total	89	100.0

that visitors who were pleased with their experiences at cultural heritage destinations were more likely to extend their stay and return for future visits. “Satisfaction” and “destination loyalty” were the keywords associated with cultural heritage tourism.

Studies have shown that when tourists have high-quality travel experiences, they develop better percep-

roles in behavior: it influences the decision-making process for destination selection and conditions subsequent behaviors such as participation (on-site experience), evaluation (satisfaction), and future behavioral intentions (intention to revisit). According to Huang, Chang and Chang (2002), a destination image is typically defined as a collection of ideas and impressions formed over time as a result of information processing from many sources, which produces a mental representation of the qualities and advantages desired from a destination.

The keywords associated with destination image include “brand image” and “service quality.” “Brand image” refers to the overall perception that consumers have of a brand or product, encompassing their thoughts, feelings, and attitudes toward it (Huang *et al.* 2021). For destinations, each one competes to attract tourists based on their unique image. Thus, if a tourist has a positive impression of a destination, they are more likely to revisit it for future trips (Huang *et al.* 2021). In both the service industry and tourism, scholars argue that “service quality” is a precursor to customer satisfaction (Khuong & Phuong 2017; Lee *et al.* 2011).

Specifically, when service quality is high, customers tend to be more satisfied (Khuong & Phuong 2017). Zeithaml, Bitner and Gremler (2006) define service quality as the consumer’s evaluation and judgment of the excellence of the service, which can also significantly impact customer satisfaction and loyalty to destinations (Kastenholz *et al.* 2018).

The following key term, perceived value, refers to the tourist’s overall evaluation of the visit’s value based on their perceptions (Chang 2018). According to Zeithaml (1988), it is “the consumer’s overall assessment of the utility of a product based on perceptions of what is received and what is given.” According to Khuong and Phuong (2017), it may also be defined in terms of pricing as the gap between what customers perceive as what they gain (utility resulting from quality) and what they sacrifice (price and other costs).

The next keyword is social media. According to Mariani, Di Felice and Mura (2016), social media has grown to be one of the most important marketing platforms in the tourist industry for both businesses and destination marketing organizations (DMOs). Social media marketing can provide a wealth of information about a destination and is a source of strategic information that can be used for developing many business strategies in the tourism sector (Mariani *et al.* 2016), including visitor satisfaction as a result of product de-

velopment, resolving visitor issues, understanding the visitor experience, analyzing competitive strategies, and monitoring the image and reputation of the destination (Pike 2015). Changing (or stimulating) tourists’ behaviors or intentions is the goal of these marketing strategies (Stylidis *et al.* 2017b; Huang *et al.* 2021), especially when there is a crisis (Li *et al.* 2018) or there is poor resident-tourist interaction. This will eventually improve the destination image held by future tourists (Liu & Tung 2017), and further achieve their loyalty and connection to the place (Huang *et al.* 2021).

The last keyword is revisit intention. The results of this evaluation and reflection process after visiting a historical place are closely related to the likelihood of returning to the location, recommending it to others, and disseminating good or negative WOM (Kempiak *et al.* 2017; Rousta & Jamshidi 2020). In light of this, it is essential to create an engaging, rewarding, and memorable experience for visitors as this may improve their loyalty and give businesses a competitive edge (Kempiak *et al.* 2017). The propensity to return can be influenced by how tourists rate their satisfaction with prior visits. The advantages received, the experience gained, and the environmental conditions are what determine the degree of consumer happiness (Maulina *et al.* 2022).

5. CONCLUSIONS AND IMPLICATIONS

Through a systematic review and detailed content analysis of 89 articles published in 54 journals between January 2010 and December 2022, this study analyzed various aspects of sustainability in CHT, focusing on destination image, perceived value, and revisit intention. The selected papers were categorized into four topics. The findings of this review can help researchers and CHT providers access relevant publications and bridge the knowledge gaps in this field.

This study identified several key findings from the literature on cultural and heritage tourism (CHT). Firstly, research on CHT has been continuously increasing over the past decade, particularly in Asia and Europe, which highlights the growing significance of CHT over time. Secondly, the interpretation and implementation of destination image and revisit intention in CHT vary among researchers. More than 40% of the papers on CHT analyzed in this study focused on destination image and revisit behavioral intention attractions, suggesting that these experiential perspectives are

essential to understanding cultural and heritage attractions. In the field of CHT, it is critical to consider interactions across the environment, economy, and society and analyze them holistically. Thirdly, this study confirmed that efforts were made to understand CHT from the customer's perspective, as evidenced by studies on tourists' loyalty and satisfaction. Ultimately, gaining tourists' hearts is crucial to becoming a sustainable cultural and heritage destination.

Finally, this study has made a valuable contribution by examining various factors and perspectives that affect the interactions between CHT, destination image, and revisit intention. This highlights the need for further research in this area, which represents a theoretical advancement from previous attempts at systematic literature review on CHT. The current paper focuses on a specialized area of tourism that links CHT, destination image, perceived value, and revisit intention, which is a relative niche topic in the field.

Despite the contributions mentioned earlier, this study has several limitations. Firstly, the review data was

limited to *Google Scholar* and *Scopus*, and studies on CHT, destination image, perceived value, and revisit intention from other sources were not included. This restricted the scope of the study and may have resulted in incomplete information on CHT. To address this limitation, future studies should consider a wider range of resources covering CHT. Secondly, the study only reviewed English-language papers on CHT, which may have resulted in a less diverse and comprehensive analysis of CHT research.

Future studies should aim to include works written in other languages to provide a more complete understanding of CHT. Lastly, due to the broad range of topics within the subject of CHT, it was not feasible to analyze all 89 studies under a single framework to identify discrepancies in the research results and suggest the reasons behind them. Thus, future research should attempt to generate a new conceptual framework and new knowledge by analyzing the agreement and disagreement of selected studies using more specific systematic review research topics in the CHT field.

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